

ISic3506

I.Sicily inscription 3506

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

necropolis of via Dottor Consoli-via Androne

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, private villa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI336684

1. □ μνημίον· ἐνθά [δε κίτε]

2. Γεώργιος παῖ[ς, ἀναπαυ]-

3. [σ] ἄ μ (ενος) μ (ηνῶν) θ, μ (ηνὶ) Μαΐω [— —]

4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645373

PHI 336684

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 51.1201

Manganaro, G. 2001. Byzantina Siciliae. *Minima Epigraphica et Papyrologica*. 4: 131-178. At 138 fig.3

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3506. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4388686>